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The Development Specifics of the Professional Training of Students

Natalya D. Koletvinova* (a), Seimbika U. Bichurina (b), Indira M. Salpykova (c)

(a), (b), (c) *Kazan Federal University, 420008, Kazan (Russia), 18 Kremlyovskaya street,
Bichurina@yandex.ru*

Abstract

The relevance of this study is due to significant changes in the field of modern education. In new aspects, the concepts of “equality” and “social justice” appeared on the background of the educational space. Modern society needs to build a qualitatively new system of training of a teacher, capable to solve fundamentally new tasks that meet the needs of the time. The psychological and pedagogical conditions of vocational training are based on a system of pedagogical actions that activate the creative, individual and personal abilities of students, ensuring the social and moral formation of the future generation. These actions are aimed at creating a cultural and educational space that forms the students' personal readiness to master a profession in the changing world of educational realities.

The purpose of research is to work out a paradigm for the development of competence of pedagogical support of students in the course of multifunctional activity with its subsequent testing.

Methods: theoretical (theoretical analysis of pedagogical, psychological, scientific methodological literature on the research topic), empirical (analysis, comparison, generalization, content choice, observation, questionnaire), pedagogical experiment (stating, forming and control stages of the experiment), method of expert assessments, statistical processing of quantitative research results.

Results: students of different levels of intellectual, knowledge and professionally oriented development were studied in the first-year academic groups. As a result of the experiment (academic year 2019-2020), we worked out a paradigm for the development of the competence of pedagogical support in the process of a multifunctional activity of a teacher in the interests of equality and social justice. The following methods were used: a thoughtful attitude to all types of activity, individualization, personal orientation, personification.

Practical relevance: a paradigm for the development of competence of pedagogical support was developed. It aims to educate future teachers with a careful and thoughtful attitude to all components of scientific and pedagogical educational resources, with capability to creatively find new aspects of situational conditioning and expediency in them, to independently use them in multifunctional pedagogical activities in the interests of equality and social justice with optimal results.

Keywords: paradigm, content, process, resources, communicative tolerance, individual, personal, interpersonal, equality, social justice.

* Corresponding author. E-mail: Bichurina@yandex.ru

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Introduction

Relevance of the problem

The problem of professional training of students for multifunctional activity in the interests of equality and social justice currently occupies one of the priority places in psychological and pedagogical science. The changing world poses new problems and challenges for the cultural and educational environment. The complexity of the multicultural process, intercultural communication, gender mismatch and subcultural deviations puts on the first place the social and moral improvement of society. It became particularly urgent to make society understand and recognize that everyone has the right to privacy and equal rights with another person. Under these conditions, the expediency to apply to the principles of equality and social justice is not in doubt (Mudrik, 2016). A theoretical analysis of the modern psychological and pedagogical understanding of the concepts “equality”, “social justice” is presented in the studies of Bimbat (2003) and Mezherikov (2004). Many scientists analyze them as psychological and pedagogical principles (Zeer, Pavlova, & Symanyuk, 2005; Trainev, 2004). Their practical implementation is associated with an analytical approach to differentiated consideration of the necessary and sufficient potential of scientific and pedagogical resources in accordance with the requirements of developing the competence of pedagogical support. Yakiminskaya (2000) and Barnes (2000) dedicated their works to the analysis of various components of scientific and pedagogical resources in the process of pedagogical support. Personality-oriented communication technologies, methods of specific situations, interactive case-methods of different levels of orientation were considered as the most appropriate. Preference was given to the multiple meaning of the motivational method and the method of individualization. Berezhnova (2010) and Shendrik (2004) consider the competency-based interaction of motivational and situationally-determined resource components as strategic guidelines for the development of the competence of pedagogical support. The study of resource components for prevention of conflicts and fundamental disagreements in various types of professional interaction is analyzed by Bolotov (2005). Multicultural activity in the conditions of a multinational contingent is studied in the works of Gabdulkhakov (2016) and Arestova (2016). Features of the emotional, value-resource components of pedagogical support are studied by Ksenzova (204) and Fopel (2002) in the context of the implementation of the requirements of equality and social justice. Bondyreva works out a theory and technology for the development of tolerant relations in the cultural and educational environment (2013) Priority is given to the principles of equality and respect for each other. Studying the basics of this issue, the modern scientific community carefully analyzes the sources of inequality in education: gender, socio-economic, cultural, special educational needs. The degree of their negative influence is analyzed, their role in modern Russian society is determined (Conn, 2010; Erofeeva, 2015). The problem of the development of social partnership is considered by

Koshuba (2014) and Kilina (2016). Prerequisites, conditions, interaction and parity are analyzed in the context of achieving positive results.

Studies of foreign scientists have recently noted a mixed interest in educational activities. Rbodes (2001) and Leavitt (1989) analyze the social orientation of training, McKenzie - cognitive independence and its characteristics (2001). Ethnic tolerance and its specificity are considered in the works of Jefferson (2002). The role of the analytical approach in training and the specifics of discussion-based interaction are presented in the works of Boström (2013) and Thomas (2012). The development of interest in independent work is explored by Hsu, Hamilton and Wang (2015).

Recently, a number of scientists analyze the use of scientific and pedagogical resources based on their respective choice and integrated interaction (Andreev, 2013; Alimova, 2015). The feasibility of the widespread use of communicative and speech resources in the aspect of the adequacy of the speech design of all types of activities to ensure the implementation of the principles of equality and social justice is investigated by Koletvinova and Bichurina (2016), Deikina (2016) and Valeeva (2010).

Thus, the training of teachers in the interests of equality and social justice is based on the categorical system of scientific and pedagogical resources that regulate the social, cultural and educational processes of professional training of students.

Literature Review

One of the main goals of modern higher education is to prepare a teacher with a high spiritual and moral potential, capable to constructively update the substantive and procedural means of pedagogical activity. Recent scientific studies developed relevant theoretical and empirical approaches to studying the problems of professional training of students at pedagogical universities for activities in the interests of equality and social justice. Strengthening the influence of the moral component of education is due to the demand of the time. "Equality", "justice", "tolerance" are considered by scientists as sources of positive influence on what is happening in the world. The purpose of using these concepts in science, according to scientists, is to create an objective picture of the educational space based on universal values (Vizgin, 2009; Stegnyy, 2010; Zeer, 2005). Currently, the educational process is implemented through the use of diverse competencies. The competence of pedagogical support has its own characteristics. Scientists consider pedagogical support as an organizational principle of interaction, a condition for personal development, an indicator of the implementation of situationally determined requirements for ensuring a positive atmosphere of multilevel multifunctional activity of a teacher (Voronov & Pismensky, 2009; Sosnin, 2013). A detailed process of the basics of pedagogical support was analyzed by Zaretskaya. The author identifies the goal, resource components, means of mutual understanding and mutual assistance, individual and personal characteristics in the context of complex interaction (Zaretskaya, 2010). Biryukova considers the process of pedagogical support in the context of the implementation of interactive, adaptive, communicative resources (2016). Psychological and pedagogical support in the context of inclusion is analyzed by Sorokoumova (2016). Preference is given to constructive, equitable interaction. In modern science, pedagogical support is considered on the basis of the use of various scientific and pedagogical resources in their multifunctionality and multidimensionality. This opens up enough space for the appropriate and purposeful use of the principles of equality and social justice (Kraevsky, 2003). The problem of forming students' professional readiness on the basis of the competency-based components of pedagogical support in the context of their

integration interaction and scientific significance is analyzed by Alekseev (2016) and Ilyin (2020). Such training contributes to the development of research qualities of future teachers. The problem of determining the significance of such resource components as motivational, emotional, situationally-determined, adaptive, personality-oriented, individualized, and adequate-speech is presented in the studies of Moskvichev (2003), Shor (2003) and Feldstein (2009). The authors pay attention to their multiple meaning, multidimensionality both in the main meaning and in the auxiliary background. Particular attention is paid to the use of emotional, situationally determined, adequate-speech resources in the context of their relevance and expediency. Gaulman considers the emotional resource in the framework of its implementation as a positive factor of influencing the audience in the context of its unification and equal interaction (2005). Gumenyuk analyzes the specifics of the implementation of motivational, adaptive, ethical and personality-oriented resources in the process of the influence of psychological culture on the state of the educational environment (2006). Babanova and Tolstov consider the motivational orientation in the process of pedagogical support as a factor of incentiveness, validity and justice (2016). Features of the development of pedagogical support competence are explored by Nefedova and Ukhova. The authors draw attention to the advisability of the systematic use of resource components in the implementation of their additional value. The positive role of situational conditioning and personal orientation in increasing the importance of research, integration and spiritual-moral orientation of professional training is considered. Their complex interaction contributes to the creation of a creative atmosphere of equality and harmony (Nefedova & Ukhova, 2006). The significance of a differentiated approach to the choice of competency resources is analyzed by Kashekova. It is emphasized that this will help to avoid conflict situations, personal tension and wariness (2014). Danilyuk considers the features of the competence resources of pedagogical support in the context of the cognitive world perception development, a vision of life in general, awareness of one's right to choose own important decision (2000). Karabut considers the internal psychological need for knowledge as a justification of own decision in the context of using motivational, personality-oriented and individualized resources (2010). Such interaction allows to develop cognitive interest and contributes to the development of personal activity of students while meeting the requirements of equality and social justice. Vyazova analyzes the problem of the appropriate choice of competency-based resources on the basis of their importance for the development of cognitive independence, individual and personal abilities of students in the context of equal intellectual communication (2007).

Foreign scientists consider the specifics of professional training in the context of the particular requirements of society. Attention is drawn to improvement of the quality of socially-oriented competencies that contribute to the self-activation of students and the development of their multidirectional independent thinking (Meyer, Haywood, Sachdev, & Faraday, 2008; Hsu, Hamilton, & Wang, 2015; Isidori, 2015). In studies, preference is given to integration and research approaches (Csorba, 2015; Rotha, & Tobin, 2001). A significant place is given to the development of personalized qualities of students (Roman & Roman, 2014; Canaleta, Vernet, Vicent, & Montero, 2014).

Thus, the pedagogical support competence can be defined as the target attitude for the integrated use of acquired knowledge in the context of the significance of time and the requirements of professional activity in the interests of equality and social justice.

Methodology

Research objectives

In the course of the research work, the following tasks were solved: 1) to study the necessary scientific-theoretical, scientific-pedagogical, philosophical-educational, scientific-psychological literature on the research problem; 2) theoretically substantiate the problem of creating the appropriate apparatus for developing the pedagogical support competencies of students; 3) to develop technologies, methodological techniques, approaches to the development of competence-accompanying abilities and skills of a multifunctional orientation based on the realization of the professional-accompanying potential of educational resources of professional training of students; 4) experimentally verify the effectiveness of professionally oriented training of abilities and skills of pedagogical support according to the developed methodology, summarize the results of the experiment.

Theoretical and Empirical Methods

To test the hypothesis we used a system-competency complex of interconnected and interacting substantive-procedural means for ensuring the development of professional multifunctional competence of pedagogical support: theoretical - analysis of multidirectional scientific literature on psychological, pedagogical, linguistic, sociological, cultural studies; analysis of educational literature; theoretical analysis of the main provisions of the proposed methodology, on the basis of which the research hypothesis was put forward; theoretical justification of the system of professionally oriented work with students to develop the competence of pedagogical support; empirical - included observation, a stating and forming pedagogical experiment, questioning, testing, analysis of the results of experimental work.

Research base

The study was conducted among first-year students of the Institute of Psychology and Education of Kazan (Volga Region) Federal University. 69 people took part in the experiment.

Research stages

The study was carried out at several stages: conducting methods of a sample of examinees; quantitative processing of the data; use of the method –Student’s t-test; interpretation and analysis of the data.

At the first stage, the process of developing students’ professional competence of pedagogical support was monitored; interviewing the students was carried out; the level of definition of professional competency-based components of pedagogical support and the level of acquiring them were established; the theoretical concept of the study was refined and adjusted. At the second stage a training experiment was conducted; on the third stage analysis, generalization and systematization of the obtained data was made; the study was formed; the research topic was presented in publications and scientific conferences.

Evaluation criteria

The study selected special evaluation criteria for determining the level of acquiring the main components of the professional competence of pedagogical support. The scale of preliminary competency-based orientation; methodology of typology of educational competence research; methodology of competency-based research on the awareness of the interaction integrity and the relationship between the development of pedagogical support competence and the competence potential of educational resources; methodology of integrative pedagogical support competence in professional activities.

The course and description of the experiment

The ascertaining stage of the experiment was conducted with first-year students (69 people) in September-October 2019. The purpose was to diagnose preliminary competency-integrative orientation. The control group (CG) consisted of 44 people. The experimental group (EG) contained 25 people. Students of both groups were asked questions of competency-based orientation in order to determine the degree of interest in the problem of professionally-oriented research, the level of knowledge and skills to apply the competencies of pedagogical support in professional activities in the interests of equality and social justice.

Students were asked the following questions:

1. Is it difficult to obtain new knowledge based on the pedagogical support competence?
2. Is it difficult for you to choose educational material with multilevel components of the pedagogical support competence?
3. Do you feel uncertain about the correct definition of competency-based types of professional activity?
4. Is it difficult for you to improve the quality of knowledge and its systematization in professional activities?
5. Does creating lessons based on the competencies of pedagogical support cause serious difficulties?

We also used methods of statistical analysis: arithmetic mean, variance; determination of the significance of differences in the values of indicators (Student's t-test). Arithmetic mean characterizes the most frequently encountered class of objects, representing the quotient of dividing the sum of various values by their number and is calculated by the formula:

$$x = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i}{N},$$

where x_i is individual values of indicator of i subject, N is a total number of subjects.

Variance (σ^2) is arithmetic mean of the squared deviations of the variable from its mean. It is calculated by the formula:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1}$$

where n is the sample size;

i is the summation index;

\bar{x} is arithmetic mean value.

In order to test the hypothesis about the reliability of differences between the average values of the indicators obtained during the study, we carried out a parametric method – Student's t-test, used to test hypotheses about the reliability of the difference in means in the analysis of quantitative data. In this study it was the case of independent samples, where the number of subjects is 69 people. Therefore, to analyze the difference in average values, the formula was applied:

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{(n_1 - 1) \cdot \sigma_1^2 + (n_2 - 1) \cdot \sigma_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \right)}}$$

Where

\bar{x}_1 is arithmetic mean of the first sample;

\bar{x}_2 is arithmetic mean of the second sample;

σ_1 is standard deviation for the first sample;

σ_2 is standard deviation for the second sample;

n_1 & n_2 are the numbers of elements in the first and second samples.

To find the critical value t , the number of degrees of freedom is determined:

$$\eta = n_1 - 1 + n_2 - 1 = (n_1 + n_2) - 2 = n - 2$$

The tested hypothesis H_0 is that the difference between the mean values of two samples is zero ($\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2 = 0$), in other words, this is the hypothesis of equality of means ($\bar{x}_1 = \bar{x}_2$). The alternative hypothesis H_1 is that this difference is nonzero ($\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2 \neq 0$), or there is a difference in sample means ($\bar{x}_1 \neq \bar{x}_2$).

Diagnostic material proposed by Tsukerman (1996) was used. The methodology of studying the characteristics of the interaction of students in the implementation of joint activities. The assessment was carried out on the basis of observation, according to the following criteria: productivity of joint activities; the ability to negotiate, to come to a common decision, the ability to convince, to argue; mutual control in the course of activities; mutual assistance; emotional attitude to joint activities. The results are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Analysis of research of students' ability to consider partner's position in the course of joint activities at the ascertaining stage.

20% of students in the experimental group showed a high level of ability to consider the partner's position, which was expressed in their ability to negotiate with each other, to reason and make general conclusions. 24% showed a medium level. 56% have a low level. Analyzing the results of the study, we can conclude that they did not try to give way to their peers, did not cooperate, acted in their own way, which indicates difficulties in the ability to listen, hear and understand each other, plan and coordinate joint activities, and mutually control each other's actions.

Data on the control group indicate that 50% of students in the control group have a low level of ability consider the partner's position in the course of joint activities, 25% have an medium level and 25% have a high level of communication skills.

Test of the self-esteem study (Schur, 1982). Analysis of the interviewing results in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Comparative analysis of students' self-esteem at the ascertaining stage

The experimental group is characterized by high self-esteem in 52% of cases; 28% have adequate self-esteem, students can explain their actions when responding, referring to real situations and achievements. 20% of this group is characterized by high anxiety and self-doubt, which provokes a low level of self-esteem. In the control group, 37% had adequate self-esteem. 50% are characterized by high self-esteem, 13% have low self-esteem. A comparative analysis led to the conclusion that students of the experimental and control groups have approximately the same level of self-esteem.

We also studied interpersonal relationships by Vandvik and Ekblad (Versaka & Gutorova, 2014). We revealed the levels of formation of communication skills and evaluation of interpersonal relationships. The results of the analysis of social status are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Social status position indicators at the ascertaining group.

The diagram shows that in the experimental group the majority belongs to the category of “rejected” (36% and 40%); 32% and 23% are “accepted,” they are active, communicative enough, but often conflictual, they easily become participants in communication, but they also easily start to conflict and refuse to interact, they are often upset and offend others, but they easily forget their insults. 32% and 37% are in the “preferred” group, but satisfaction with the relationship is low. Most students are not adapted, constrained in communication, do not show initiative, have little interest in new contacts, are mainly grouped into separate small groups, and often show injustice.

The next stage of the study was the experimental work aimed at the formation of equality and social justice. The components of the content of the student’s social development in society are self-esteem, social status, interpersonal relations, cooperation, communicative tolerance, equality, social justice, which are formed purposefully in the educational process of the university by means of the students entering the public communications.

At the end of the formative phase, a second survey was conducted. The analysis of the study results according to the Tsuckerman’s (1996) method showed that the students of the experimental group began to take into account the position of their peers in the course of joint work, learned how to control their emotions, show justice (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The results of the analysis of the ability to consider the partner's position after the experiment.

68% of students in the experimental group showed a high level of ability consider the partner's position, which was expressed in their ability to negotiate with each other, to reason and draw general conclusions on the made decisions. 30% (in CG) and 2% (EG) of students showed medium and low levels. In the control group the high level is shown by 48%, the medium level by 41%, and the low level by 11%.

Students of the experimental group demonstrated the ability to coordinate their actions, the ability to negotiate, support and accept each other's opinion, show respect and justice (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Post- experiment self-assessment results.

We observe significant changes in students of the experimental group at the level of self-esteem, so 70% have adequate self-esteem, explain their actions, referring to real situations and achievements, believe that the teacher's assessment is just. In the control group, 40% of students have adequate self-esteem. A comparative analysis allowed us to conclude that the vast majority of students in the experimental group had an adequate level of self-esteem. Analysis results in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Comparison of students from the EG and CG.

The diagram shows that 66% of "accepted" in experimental group became active, sociable, easily become participants of communication. The level of development of communication skills became high. The team is collaborative, there are no isolated students. In the control group 8% of the "rejected" remained.

Table 7. Results of the analysis of differences between groups according to the Mann-Whitney criteria

Research methods	EG (x.cp)	CG (x.cp.)	U _{emp}	U _{kr}
Method "Mittens"	2,3	2,62	89	-
Test "Stairs"	2,1	2,5	95	-
Method "Two houses"	2,0	2,3	91	-

Thus, it should be noted that the measures not only improved interpersonal relationships among students, but also helped to improve the emotional background in the group, the students' well-being and mood. The

principles of equality and social justice began to dominate in the relationship. The analysis of the results showed that in the experimental group, for all indicators, the high and medium levels have higher values than in the control group. This confirms the effectiveness of the conducted experimental work using active and interactive forms of organization of classes and trainings.

Further to the study and analysis of the state of professionally-competent training of students it can be noted that the experimental group has a higher level of pedagogical support competence than the control group. This indicates the effectiveness of the developed means of formation of the pedagogical support competence, contributing to the extension of their scientific and theoretical potential in the aspect of the multifunctional activity of the teacher, independent thinking and increasing the level of professional readiness in the context of finding non-standard solutions to the problems of scientific and educational competency issues. An important difference was the level of professionally-competent research training of students, based on the inclusion of special metacomponents in the content-procedural training tools. In the context of the competency-based orientation of professional training of students, the experimental group showed the best results, since various incentives for motivational justification and personal interest in developing the competence of pedagogical support were used in the context of further obtaining high results of professional activity.

Results

Educational paradigm for the development of pedagogical support competencies was developed. It was based on the formation of students' cognitive needs for a meaningful and thoughtful attitude to the choice of scientific and pedagogical resources in order to implement the modern requirements of the educational process. Effective methods of the pedagogical support competence development include a differentiated approach to the use of resource components in the context of their optimal expediency for pedagogical activity in the interests of equality and social justice. The practice-oriented activity of students confirmed the effectiveness of the chosen methods and forms of professional training aimed at developing the creative abilities of students and allowing them to consciously navigate the surrounding reality and make independent decisions.

Discussions

The problem of development of professional training of students in the interests of equality and social justice currently occupies one of the priority places. The scientific community analyzes it taking into account the changes in society (Grigorovich, 2015; Kornetov, 2016). In this context, a rethinking of the general structure of the organization of student education is carried out in the aspect of social and moral improvement. Ethical education as the basis of the social formation of the individual is considered in detail by Kapustina (2010). The author notes the appropriateness of new requirements to the social order for the education of the younger generation. This problem affects the interests of the vast majority of the population. The priorities and values of modern education are studied in the work of Popova (2012). The study of Platonov is devoted to the special aspects of the scientific work. He considers certain features of social problems (2016). Interactivity as one of the leading areas is considered by Bukatov (2017). The potential of the collective as a cultural and educational environment of the individual is considered by Zaitseva (2008), Abramova (2010). The feasibility of using the technological foundations of the social formation of personality is analyzed by Petukhov (2010). Innovative interpretations of pedagogical

technologies are studied in the work of Elina, Kovtun and Rodionova (2015). Feldstein analyzes psychological and pedagogical science as a resource for the development of modern society (Feldstein, 2009). A special place in professional training is occupied by ethical culture. It is associated with moral, intellectual and social changes (Lukashenko, 2013). Many scientists consider the student professional training in the context of the implementation of the equality and social justice principles in relation to the real process of life. This requires improving the quality of higher education, moral and aesthetic education, and ethnocultural development of future teachers (Krupnik & Kiselnikova, 2014). This issue is reflected in the research of foreign scientists. Belarusian scientists analyze it in the context of “man, education, culture” (Zhigalova, 2014). Romanian researcher Bejenaru analyzes the relationship of moral education with the problem of reevaluation of values (2014). The role of preventive measures in the process of education of young people, the importance of motivational conditioning in multilevel educational activities are analyzed by Meyer, Haywood, Sachdev and Faraday (2008). A study of the social orientation of training is presented in the works of Cunningham (2010) and Virtanen (2008). The analysis of the literature allows us to note the diversity and significance of this issue.

However, a deep comprehensive and multi-level study of the problem of professional training of students in the interests of equality and social justice is not noted. Among the disadvantages are the desire of some authors to limit themselves to general provisions without evidence-based analysis, the lack of a clear indication of the situational conditioning of the use of ethnocultural components in the context of adaptive analysis. There is no complete notion of the teacher’s professional and personal actions to create optimal conditions for the implementation of the principles of equality and social justice, taking into account feedback.

Conclusion

The study showed that the development of the pedagogical support competence depends on many factors: the development of an educational paradigm based on an analytical approach to scientific and pedagogical resources, the choice of methods and complex tasks that meet the requirements of equality and social justice. The study showed the effectiveness of the selected scientific and pedagogical resources and methods for the professional sphere of activity. A fairly high level of acquiring competence-relevant components necessary for multifunctional activity is noted.

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